

SYNTHESES IN THE ACRIDINE SERIES. PART VI*. N-SUBSTITUTED 2-CHLORO-7-NITRO-9-AMINOACRIDINES

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Ten N-substituted 2-chloro-7-nitro 9-aminoacridines have been prepared with a view to testing their antimalarial properties.

Magidson, Grigorowsky and Galperin (*J. Gen. Chem. Russ.*, 1938, 8, 56) have found that when the methoxy group in the 2 position in the atebtrin molecule [2-methoxy-6-chloro-9-(ω -diethylaminoisoamyl)aminoacridine dihydrochloride] is substituted by a chlorine atom, the antimalarial activity is not affected. Again, Magidson and Grigorowsky (*Ber.*, 1936, 61, 396) have noticed that the antimalarial activity is considerably increased if a nitro group is introduced in the acridine nucleus at position 6 or 7, as compared to cases where no substituent is present. The improvement is more marked, if the entrant nitro group occupies the 7 position (and not the 6). A similar transfer of the chlorine atom is accompanied with a considerable decrease of the antimalarial properties (*cf.* Feldmann and Kopeliowitsch, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1935, 273, 488). It should be interesting to prepare compounds of the type (I), having a chlorine atom in position 2, augmented by the presence of a nitro group at position 7 and carrying a dialkylamino-alkyl grouping at position 9.

King and Work (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 401) found that when the sum of the carbon atoms of the N-dialkyl group in the series N-dialkylaminoethyl-6-methoxyquinolyl carbinois lay between 8 and 12, the activity was maximum. The higher and lower homologues were found to be inactive. We have therefore also substituted N-dipropyl-, N-dibutyl- or N-diamyl-amino and N-piperidino group in place of the terminal N-diethyl-amino grouping (as present in atebtrin).

2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid has been condensed with *p*-chloroaniline to give 4-nitro-4'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic acid. This was converted into 7-nitro-2:9-dichloroacridine by treatment with POCl_3 . A number of 9-dialkylamino-alkylaminoacridines were prepared by condensing 7-nitro-2:9-dichloroacridine with the appropriate amine, followed by the purification of the free base by the decomposition of its soluble acetate (Method I; *cf.* D. R. P. 553,072). In the case of higher substituted 9-aminoacridines, found to be insoluble in dilute acetic acid, anhydrous potassium carbonate was added to the reaction mixture (Method II; *cf.* Burckhalter *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2012). The yields obtained were between 40 and 60%

* Part V of this series has been published in the *Jour. Lahore Phil. Soc.*, 1946, 8, 41.

and considerable quantities of acridine were obtained as undesirable byproduct by the hydrolysis of 7-nitro-2:9-dichloroacridine. Condensation of various amines through 4-nitro-4'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxyl chloride, and ring-closure of the resulting amide with phosphoryl chloride, however, gave better yields.

The various acridine bases obtained by condensation are bright red in colour, while their salts are yellow. The dihydrochlorides are moderately soluble in water, though the solubility increases in acidic medium. Some of the hydrochlorides hydrolyse in aqueous solution and the red insoluble bases are liberated. The effect is more prominent when an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride is boiled. Addition of a few drops of hydrochloric acid gives a yellow solution. This may be due to the hydrolysis of the weak hydrochloride into the free red base in aqueous solution.

Similarly when the hydrochloride solutions are treated with sodium acetate, the free bases are liberated.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Nitro-4'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxylic Acid.—2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzoic acid (10 g.) was mixed and ground well with *p*-chloroaniline (16 g.) and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 155°-160° for 30 minutes, with continuous trituration. The dark green sticky mass obtained was boiled with 250 c.c. of 10% hydrochloric acid and filtered hot. The insoluble residue was extracted with 1 litre of boiling 5% ammonia solution (charcoal). The sparingly soluble yellow ammonium salt was decomposed with hydrochloric acid. After drying it was crystallised from glacial acetic acid or absolute ethanol in sulphur yellow glistening needles, m. p. 283-84°, yield 86%. (cf. also Linnell, *Quart. J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1942, 15, 31, m. p. 284-85°). During this condensation a little dark green residue was always left, which was insoluble in hot ammonia solution. It appears to be the decarboxylation product of the above acid.

4-Nitro-4'-chlorodiphenylamine-6-carboxyl chloride was prepared by refluxing the above acid with PCl₅ (1:1 molecular ratio) in benzene for about 20 minutes, when a clear yellow solution was obtained. This was cooled and the yellow product separating was recrystallised from a small volume of benzene as yellow powder, m. p. 135-36°, yield 75%. (Found: N, 9.27. C₁₃H₈O₃N₂Cl₂ requires N, 9.0 per cent). No acid chloride was found when the reaction was carried in absolute petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°).

7-Nitro-2:9-dichloroacridine.—The above acid on treatment with phosphoryl chloride in the usual way was converted into the acridine. It was crystallised from absolute benzene in small, yellow needles, m. p. 208-09°, yield 75%. (Found: N, 9.71. C₁₃H₈O₂N₂Cl₂ requires N, 9.56 per cent). The acridine gradually hydrolysed to the corresponding acridone with evolution of hydrochloric acid gas. It was used for condensation a few hours after its crystallisation.

2-Chloro-7-nitro-9-(γ-diethylaminopropyl)aminoacridine (Method I).—A mixture of 7-nitro-2:9-dichloroacridine (3.11 g., mol.) and freshly distilled phenol (14 g.)

was warmed on a steam-bath, until solution was effected. To the hot phenolic solution was added γ -diethylaminopropylamine (1.3 g., 1 mol.). Heating was continued for another 3 hours with occasional shaking. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into excess of 2*N*-sodium hydroxide solution. The red base was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was shaken with 5% acetic acid solution and the chloroform layer rejected. The acetate was decomposed with dilute alkali and the base taken up in chloroform (40 c. c.). After drying over potassium carbonate it was diluted with anhydrous ether (50 c. c.) and the dihydrochloride was precipitated by the addition of alcoholic hydrogen chloride as a semi-solid mass. After leaving overnight, it was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and acetone as bright yellow powder, m. p. 212-14° (d). It is soluble in water, giving an orange coloured solution, which turns yellow on the addition of a few drops of hydrochloric acid. (Found : N, 12.43. $C_{20}H_{23}O_2N_4Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 12.10 per cent).

2-Chloro-7-nitro-9-(δ -diethylaminobutyl)aminoacridine dihydrochloride was prepared by the condensation of 7-nitro-2:9-dichloroacridine and δ -diethylaminobutylamine according to Method I. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol in yellow glistening microcrystalline powder, m. p. 224-26° (d). It is moderately soluble in water. (Found : N, 12.12. $C_{21}H_{25}O_2N_4Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 11.82 per cent).

2-Chloro-7-nitro-9-(ϵ -diethylaminoamyl)aminoacridine dihydrochloride was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and acetone as a yellow powder, m. p. 235-36° (d). (Found : N, 11.05. $C_{22}H_{27}O_2N_4Cl$, 2HCl requires, N, 11.48 per cent). Considerable quantities of acridine (40%) were obtained during this reaction. Much better results were obtained through the acid chloride. 4-Nitro-4'-chloro-diphenylamine-6-carboxyl chloride (3.11 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in 60 c. c. of dry benzene. ϵ -Diethylaminoamylamine (1.58 g., 1 mol.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 30 minutes to complete the amide formation. To effect the ring-closure, phosphoryl chloride (10 c. c.) was added and refluxing continued for another 3 hours. During this time the solid dihydrochloride of the condensation product had separated. Benzene was decanted off and the residue washed with absolute ether. It was decomposed with alkali and the red base extracted with chloroform. The dihydrochloride was precipitated as described.

*2-Chloro-7-nitro-9-(γ -di-*n*-propylaminopropyl)aminoacridine dihydrochloride* was prepared according to Method I. It was crystallised from a large volume of absolute alcohol in glistening yellow crystals, m. p. above 320° (d). The alcoholic filtrate on dilution with ether gave more of the substance, m. p. 236-38°. It appears to be a hydrate (with ether of crystallisation), as shown by a low nitrogen analysis. The anhydrous substance, as obtained by crystallisation from absolute alcohol, analysed well. (Found : N, 11.25. $C_{22}H_{27}O_2N_4Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 11.48 per cent). It is sparingly soluble in water, undergoing hydrolysis.

*2-Chloro-7-nitro-9-(γ -di-*n*-butylaminopropyl)aminoacridine* (Method II).—7-Nitro-2:9-dichloroacridine (3.11 g., 1 mol.) and phenol (12 g.) were warmed to effect solution. Anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.69 g., 1 mol.) was added and the mixture heated for 10 minutes. Di-*n*-butylaminopropylamine (1.86 g., 1 mol.) was added and the mixture heated at 100° for 3 hours. After cooling, it was added to

150 c.c. of chloroform and phenol was removed by washing with sodium hydroxide solution. After drying over anhydrous potassium carbonate, chloroform was evaporated to half its volume and 50 c.c. of ether added. Addition of alcoholic hydrogen chloride precipitated the dihydrochloride which was crystallised from absolute alcohol in yellow glistening crystals (with alcohol of crystallisation). The compound did not show a sharp melting point and could not be made anhydrous by heating at 100° in an air-oven for 15 hours. When it was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether (as a yellow powder), it melted above 330° with previous darkening at 270° . The analytical results were satisfactory. (Found : N, 10.74. $C_{24}H_{32}O_2N_4Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 10.86 per cent). The dihydrochloride is very sparingly soluble in water and also shows hydrolysis effect.

2-Chloro-7-nitro-9-(γ -di-n-amylaminopropyl)aminoacridine dihydrochloride was prepared according to Method II. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol in yellow crystals, m. p. above 310° (decomp.), yield 35%. A better yield (60%) was obtained through the acid chloride. It is sparingly soluble in water. (Found : N, 10.15. $C_{28}H_{38}O_2N_4Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 10.30 per cent).

2-Chloro-7-nitro-9-(γ -piperidinopropyl)aminoacridine.—The condensation was carried out according to Method I. The reaction mixture was poured into ether. The solid product obtained was collected on suction, and thoroughly washed with ether. It was then treated with excess of 5% acetic acid solution. The soluble acetate was filtered free of any insoluble acridone and then decomposed with alkali. The free acridine base was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and chloroform into ruby-red glistening slender needles, m. p. $199-200^{\circ}$. The base is soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid giving a yellow solution. (Found : N, 14.00. $C_{21}H_{23}O_2N_4Cl$ requires N, 14.05 per cent).

2-Chloro-7-nitro-9-(2'-methoxy-6'-chloro-9'-acridyl)aminoacridine.—A mixture of 7-nitro-2:9-dichloroacridine (1 g.), phenol (5 g.) and 2-methoxy-6-chloro-9-aminoacridine (0.83 g.) was heated at 100° for 4 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into excess of dilute sodium hydroxide solution. After trituration, the red product obtained was filtered and washed with water. After drying it was crystallised from absolute alcohol in small orange-red crystals, m. p. $192-94^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 10.62. $C_{27}H_{18}O_2N_4Cl_2$ requires N, 10.87 per cent).